

yiŋ, acwŋ t iŋ0acwŋar;ajz&wŋrsm \ pum;ozŋpyŋ eS h pŋoŋciŋrsm

at;at;jriŋ

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ppmwŋrŋonŋ yiŋ, acwŋ t iŋ0acwŋ ar;ajz&wŋrsm \ pum;ozŋpyŋ eS h pŋoŋciŋrsm;ullazmŋkwŋe&nŋŋŋ fi avŋmwiŋyŋm;ygŋonŋ xŋbŋvŋmwiŋyŋ&mŋwŋŋ f pum;ozŋpyŋ eŋi toŋt&nŋftaŋoŋwŋt wŋt pyŋ? Asnŋf,wŋb&wŋt wŋt pyŋ? Asnŋf,wŋb&uŋŋ t wŋt pyŋrsm;ull pŋpŋwiŋyŋm;ygŋonŋ pŋoŋciŋwŋŋf pum;ozŋpŋoŋciŋeŋ h pum;vŋŋ zŋbŋpŋoŋciŋwŋŋull pŋpŋvŋmwiŋyŋoŋ;ygŋrŋŋ

aonŋtsuŋhŋgŋ nŋrsm - yiŋ, acwŋ t iŋ0acwŋ ar;ajz&wŋrsm oŋŋŋŋ oŋŋwŋŋ oŋŋvŋŋ? Asnŋf,wŋb&wŋŋ Asnŋf,wŋb&uŋŋ pŋoŋciŋf/

edŋeŋ

jreŋmpmŋyŋonŋŋ f wŋŋf yiŋ, acwŋonŋ uAsm v uŋp w iŋ zŋŋjyŋŋ t iŋ0acwŋwŋŋ uAsm v uŋŋ yŋŋwŋwŋuŋv m aŋuŋm iŋ avŋm w aŋwŋŋŋ yŋgŋonŋŋ t iŋ0acwŋŋ p m q ŋ t r s m ; p l o n i & [e f p m q ŋ t r s m ; j z p ŋ u o n f t w ŋ ŋ y ŋ ŋ u A s m o n i t x e f ; u m ; q ŋ ŋ z p ŋ o n i / y ŋ ŋ u A s m e n f ; w i t z ŋ r s m ; a o m u A s m t r ŋ t p m ; r ŋ ŋ & w j z p ŋ o n i / & w ŋ u A s m w ŋ ŋ a u s k a p & w ŋ a r m i b ŋ ŋ w ŋ r , f o ŋ ŋ w ŋ p p f c ŋ w ŋ b ŋ m ; w ŋ ŋ & w ŋ o ŋ u m ; w ŋ ŋ & w ŋ r ŋ h a w m & w ŋ r ŋ w ŋ ŋ & w ŋ ar;ajz&wŋŋŋ l i & w ŋ u A s m t r ŋ t p m ; r s m ; p ŋ ŋ a y : x e f ; c ŋ y g o n i / & w ŋ u A s m \ t p o n i p w ŋ * A v t r w ŋ u a r ; j y ŋ a y g u ŋ ŋ q & m a w m ŋ u a j z ŋ u m ; a o m a r ; a j z & w j z i h p c ŋ y g o n i / a r ; a j z & w ŋ r s m ; u l l y i ŋ , a c w ŋ t i ŋ 0 a c w ŋ a w m i ŋ i ŋ a c w ŋ u e f a b m i ŋ a c w ŋ w ŋ w ŋ ŋ a w ŋ y g o n i / o ŋ ŋ a o m f a r ; a j z & w ŋ r s m ; o n i v l o e n f ; a o m u A s m r s m ; j z p ŋ y g o n i / x ŋ b ŋ v l o e n f ; o n h a r ; a j z & w ŋ r s m ; \ t o ŋ t & n ŋ f t a o ŋ e ŋ p ŋ o ŋ a & ; z ŋ b ŋ y ŋ r s m ; u l l a v ŋ m a z m ŋ k w ŋ w i f y y g r ŋ ŋ

ohwoe&nŋŋŋ tsuŋeŋh toŋŋŋeŋŋ

t iŋ 0 a c w ŋ a r ; a j z & w ŋ r s m ; \ p u m ; o z ŋ p y ŋ e S h p ŋ o ŋ c i f t o ŋ r s m ; u l l a z m ŋ k w ŋ v ŋ o m & n ŋ ŋ ŋ ŋ t s u f z p y g o n i / a r ; a j z & w ŋ u A s m r s m ; \ a z m f y v ŋ o m t e u f t " y ŋ ŋ , E S h o ŋ E l e f ; x m ; o n i p u m ; o w ŋ v l u z u r ŋ ŋ ŋ ŋ a & ; [e f y n m y ŋ ŋ f j z i h p p ŋ w i f y x m ; y g ŋ o n i / p ŋ o ŋ c i f w ŋ ŋ f r n ŋ o n f t w ŋ ŋ p ŋ o ŋ c i f o ŋ ŋ a b u m i f r n ŋ o n p ŋ o ŋ c i f u l l o ŋ x m ; a b u m i f a v ŋ m w i f y x m ; y g ŋ o n i /

pum;ozŋpyŋŋ eŋ

b m o m p u m ; [a o m t p w ŋ t y ŋ ŋ f w ŋ ŋ A s n f o ŋ o & o ŋ ŋ b o n h p u m ; o ŋ r s m ; y g o i f y g o n i / u A s m z ŋ ŋ m w ŋ ŋ f p u m ; o j z p o n h A s n f o ŋ o & o ŋ r s m ; u l l t r ŋ t r z ŋ p y c i f j z i h u A s m \

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